

5 kg/ha. Rainfall during the crop season (Feb-Jun) was 104 mm but only 32 mm was received within 42 d after sowing.

Table 2 shows the mean grain yield in a decreasing order of 0.53 t for black gram, 0.41 t for soybean, 0.33 t for groundnut, 0.28 t for green gram, and 0.21 t/ha for gingelly. Better performance of black gram was ascribed to its shorter duration, uniform and synchronous flowering, and completion of harvest in two pickings. The results indicated that a third crop of pulse would fit in a commonly used two crop rice - rice rotation. *S*

Table 2. Grain yield of first, second, and third crops during 1984-85, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamuduram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cropping pattern	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	First crop	Second crop	Third crop
TKM9-IR20-Black gram	4.52	4.11	0.53
TKM9-IR20-Green gram	4.38	4.18	0.28
TKM9-IR20-Soybean	4.33	4.26	0.41
TKM9-IR20-Gingelly	4.57	4.07	0.21
TKM9-IR20-Groundnut	4.28	4.11	0.34
IR20-ADT36-Black gram	3.28	3.34	0.52
IR20-ADT36-Green gram	3.17	3.37	0.27
IR20-ADT36-Soybean	3.08	3.45	0.40
IR20-ADT36-Gingelly	3.04	3.47	0.20
IR20-ADT36-Groundnut	3.05	3.70	0.32
CD (5%)	0.41	0.55	-

Organic manures as a nitrogen source in a rice - wheat rotation

M.S. Maskina, C.S. Khind, and O.P. Meelu, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, India

The effect of poultry, piggery, and farmyard manures as substitute N was evaluated at the PAU farm during kharif 1984 and 1985. The soil (pH 8.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, organic C 0.25%, total N 0.03%) of the experimental field is loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with an average percolation rate of 5 mm/h. The rice variety was PR106.

Poultry, piggery, and farmyard manures containing 1.50, 1.36, and 0.51% N were applied at 5.0, 5.5, and 15 t/ha, each adding about 75 kg N/ha. The manures also were supplemented with 2 levels (80 and 120 kg N/ha) of urea N applied in 3 equal splits: at transplanting and at 21 and 42 d after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 12.5 kg K/ha was applied at last puddling.

Yields with poultry manure without fertilizer N were twice as high as those with other manures (see figure). With fertilizer N, poultry manure also outyielded farmyard and piggery manures. Yields with poultry manure and 80 kg N/ha were as high as those with 160 kg N/ha alone. Yields with farmyard and piggery manures and 80 kg N/ha were almost equal to those with 120 kg N/ha alone. The results

Rice yield (t/ha)

Rice yields with organic manures substituting for N (mean of 2 yr).

suggest that substituting organic manure for 40 to 80 kg fertilizer N/ha is feasible, depending upon the nature of the organic manure.

The residual effects of these manures on a following wheat crop (with 90 kg N and 13 kg P/ha underdose) also were compared. With poultry manure applied to the previous rice crop, wheat yield was 1180 kg/ha more; with farmyard

manure, 770 kg/ha more; with piggery manure, 660 kg/ha more. These yields were comparable to yield with the recommended 120 kg N and 26 kg P/ha applied to the wheat crop. Results indicate that application of any one manure to rice gives a residual effect equivalent to 30 kg N and 13 kg P/ha in wheat. Poultry manure had the largest residual effect. *S*